

MAGNETIC FIELD DETECTION USING AN ACTUATED MICRO-SENSOR BASED ON PIEZO-RESISTOR TRANSDUCTION

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ABSTRACT

The measurement of an external magnetic field includes the implementation of as simple technique capable for transducing the deflection induced by the Lorentz force, into electrical signals via advanced piezo-resistive technology. The piezo-resistive effect, which is highly dependent on the crystal lattice orientation, doping characteristics, and concentration levels of silicon, forms the core of this investigation. Polysilicon, renowned for its piezo-resistive properties, is utilized as the transducer material in this study. This paper focuses on the characterization of the transduction mechanisms and assesses the performance of several samples of piezo-resistors in converting cantilever displacement into measurable voltage outputs. The research outcomes illustrate that the variation in resistance (ΔR_p %) exhibits a nonlinear relationship for different cantilever beam deflections. Utilizing a polysilicon piezo-resistor configured in a Wheatstone bridge, the proposed system effectively translates mechanical deflections into electrical measurements across different voltages and cantilever geometries. Remarkably, the highest sensitivity of approximately 64 mV/mT was attained, without amplification, using a thin polysilicon beam of 0.6 μm thickness embedded into a 2 μm thick silicon cantilever.

Keywords: Magnetic field, Piezo-resistive, cantilever, Wheatstone bridge

1. Introduction

Micro-electro-mechanical systems (MEMS) technology is a valued and noticeable field of engineering due to its wide range of applications and significant effects in modern industries. MEMS can be more properly defined as the combination of mechanical elements, actuators, sensors, and electronic circuits on a shared silicon substrate, fabricated using micro-manufacturing techniques which permits them to operate as comprehensive systems with innovative abilities in actuation, sensing, and processing of the signal. The simplest way to introduce MEMS is by breaking down the abbreviation [1-2]. "Micro" denotes the devices with dimensions typically in the micrometer scale, meaning that at least one of their physical dimensions is on the order of microns. The word electro highlights the incorporation of electrical energy, used for sensing, actuation, and processing of the signal. This includes driving mechanical motion or controlling electronics for electrical signal filtration and amplification. On the other hand, the word Mechanical shows that these devices include some form of mechanical movement, operation, or

functionality. Finally, the word systems, emphasizes that MEMS are not separate mechanisms, but relatively complicated combined systems designed to achieve consistent tasks [1-4].

- **Micro Fabricated Cantilevers**

Recently, the micro fabricated cantilevers were introduced as mechanical transducers for a range of sensing applications. The use of cantilevers for these applications provides many advantages which include the low production costs, high sensitivity and compressed size. Actually the cantilevers comprise the microscopic beams that free to move at one end and are fixed the other end. They are made-up using the techniques of silicon microfabrication [5]. There are various shapes of the cantilever beam, these include V-shaped, U-shaped and single rectangular shape. Generally, cantilever systems are used to measure various physical quantities Depending on the application. However, the U-shaped and V-shaped cantilevers are usually implemented in magnetic field sensing. On the other hand, the single rectangular shape cantilevers are usually applied for chemical sensing and bimolecular analysis. There are two operation modes of cantilever sensors, the static and dynamic. In Static cantilevers, the cantilever deflects in response to an external force such as pressure, chemical interaction, and stress in the surface. **Static cantilevers** are favorite for direct and simple deflection measurements. In dynamic cantilevers, the cantilevers are excited at or near their resonance frequencies where the responses are monitored. They are used in applications that required high sensitivity. For example, they are used in the detection of the changes in the force or small mass [6-7].

- **The Piezoresistive Materials**

The piezoresistive materials are usually fabricated from silicon. When these materials are subjected to mechanical stress they reveal variation in the electrical resistance. This mechanical effect converted into electrical signals using suitable sensors. The piezoresistive materials are considered as passive components since they require an external voltage source to measure the change in resistance [8]. These materials have high sensitivity and are very accuracy in detecting the mechanical stress, also they are capable to integrate with the semiconductor electronics which is considered as the important benefit for MEMS devices [9].

- **The Electrostatic Actuators**

Currently the electrostatic actuators are extensively implemented in MEMS applications, while electromagnetic force, particularly the Lorentz force, remains the possible substitute for powering micro-machines [10-11]. This study concentrates on a straightforward and effective system for measuring weak magnetic fields using Lorentz force-based actuation. Basically, the principle of the Lorentz force drives the movement of the U-shaped cantilever when placed in a magnetic field [12]. As shown in Figure 1, this force is generated when an aluminum U-shaped cantilever carrying an electric current is placed in a magnetic field. Each moving charge within the current-carrying wire experiences a Lorentz force, which together generates a macroscopic force on the wire. In case of a straight, stationary wire, the generated force can be described by Equation1 [11-13].

$$\vec{F} = \vec{I}L \times \vec{B} \quad (1)$$

Where:

- **F** represents the force on the wire (in Newton's),
- **I** represents the current through the wire (in Amperes),
- **L** is the length of the wire within the magnetic field (in Meters),
- $\times$ denotes the cross-product
- **B** denotes the magnetic field vector (in Tesla)

The Lorentz force acting on a U-shaped cantilever produce an effect that causes it to bend and deflect depending on both the external magnetic field direction and the flow of the current through the cantilever. Figure 1 demonstrates a situation where the magnetic field and the current are vertical at the U-shaped cantilever base, whereas at the arms they are antiparallel or parallel to each other [14].

In this case, the Lorentz force acts on the cantilever base, as persistent by the right-hand rule, while no considerable force is applied to the arms. As shown in Figure, when a direct current is implemented, then cantilever deflects upwards due to static mode effect. On the other hand, when an alternating current is applied, the cantilever vibrates up and down due to a motion categorized as dynamic mode [14-15]. The response of the vibrating system depends on the relationship between the frequency of the applied periodic force and the cantilever system natural frequency.

For example, if a mass-spring system is moved and then released, it will oscillate at its natural frequency. When an external periodic force is applied at this frequency, the amplitude of the system's response will considerably increase, leading to highest displacement of the cantilever. This enlargement of motion is called the resonance which represents the fundamental principle applied in resonant sensors. Usually resonance results in the maximum sensitivity of the sensor, as the highest displacement corresponds to the maximum sensitivity to detect the magnetic field or other forces [10, 11-13].

- **Theory of Piezoresistive Transducers**

The general relation between the relative change of the resistance and the change in the resistivity (ρ) for polysilicon is given by the Equation2 [16]:

$$\frac{dR}{R} = \frac{d\rho}{\rho} \quad (2)$$

Equation2 denotes that any comparative change in resistance is directly corresponding to the equivalent relative change in the resistivity of the material.

Generally, the material electrical resistance is governed by its shape, intrinsic resistivity and

dimensions, for example, the resistance of a rod having cross-sectional area (A) and length (L) is described by the Equation2 shown below.

$$R = \frac{\rho L}{A} \quad (3)$$

Therefore, the change in the material resistance (ΔR) is directly proportional to the change in its resistivity ($\Delta\rho$) [16-17].

By implementing the simulation software, the results will normally be obtained in percent of the unstressed value of the resistance. This relationship can be defined as shown in Equation4 for percentage change:

$$\Delta R\% = \frac{\text{Stressed}-\text{Unstressed}}{\text{Unstressed}}\% \quad (4)$$

Such that the percentage change in resistance between the stressed and unstressed states is denoted by $\Delta R\%$.

The resistance actual change in Ohms shown Equation5 can be calculated using Equation2.

$$\Delta R_{\rho}\% = \frac{\Delta R\%}{100} \times R \quad (5)$$

Equation5 allows the precise calculation of the changes in resistance based on the percentage variations, this provides a practical method for measuring exactly how the mechanical stress influences the piezo-resistive materials resistance.

2. Design and Fabrication of Piezoresistor

In this study the CoventorWare software is utilized to perform finite element simulations associated to the design, fabrication and analysis of the micro-machined U-shaped cantilevers. This software enables for numerous simulation models and system level optimization by offering wide-ranging control over device parameters that makes it ideal for simulating micro-machined devices with suppleness and precision. It is mainly recognized for its finite element analysis abilities, which allows the researches and engineers to simulate the physical performance of micromachined structures and systems. CoventorWare enables precise estimates of how MEMS devices perform under numerous conditions that helps to modernize the development process by decreasing the need of the high cost prototyping [17-18].

The combination of piezoresistive material inside a U-shaped cantilever beam is demonstrated in Figure 1 where an aluminum layer is placed on the top of the beam to serve as a layer of conduction. This arrangement enables the electrical connectivity needed for signal transduction.

Figure1: U-shaped Cantilever Incorporated with Piezoresistors [6]

On the other hand, Figure 2 illustrates the cross-sectional view of the arm width and arm length of the cantilever beam, which emphasizes the incorporation of polysilicon piezoresistor inside the structure of silicon in the U-shaped cantilever [17].

The physical dimensions of the piezoresistor which include the length, width and thickness are directly influenced its resistance value. This variation in resistance plays an essential part in converting the mechanical phenomenon such as strain into an electrical signal. Particularly, when the cantilever is affected by some sort of mechanical stress, the resistance of the piezoresistor significantly changed. This change will be fed to the Wheatstone bridge circuit. Then the bridge circuit converts the variation in the piezoresistor resistance to electrical signal [16-18].

Figure2: Cross-sectional view of the arm width and length of the U-shaped Cantilever Embedded with Polysilicon Piezoresistor [16]

To match parameters of the process as for example: diffusion depth, the user can independently

control the process-dependent geometry of each resistor. In a two-step method, the CoventorWare software initially solves the beam mechanical problem and then implements the resulting stress data in order to obtain the variation in the piezoresistive. Figure 3 demonstrates the setup of the beam and the piezoresistor boundary conditions.

Figure3: The Setup of the Cantilever Beam and the Piezoresistor Boundary Conditions.
(A) Combined Model (B) Cantilevered Beam (C) The Piezoresistor

Once the piezoresistor part is designed, the original value of the resistance (in ohms) is determined by applying a 5 voltage source to the piezoresistor model, as shown in Figure 4. This process is essential to accurately define the base resistance of the piezoresistor before applying any mechanical stress, confirming that the component functions as proposed within the designed parameters [19].

Figure4: The Piezoresistor Model Voltage Application

In this study the *CoventorWare* software is used to define the percentage change in current through the piezoresistor when the deflection is applied to the cantilever. Due to this variation, the resulting change in the piezoresistor resistance (ΔR_p) can be calculated. The *CoventorWare* software initially calculates the current flowing through the piezoresistor during unstressed condition, and then it calculates the value of the current when the stress is applied. Then it compares the two values in order to calculate the percentage difference to provide the effect of mechanical stress on the device [20].

As mentioned in the previous sections, the piezoresistor resistance depends basically of its physical dimensions. Any variation in this resistance can be converted to corresponding electrical signal by using the Wheatstone bridge configuration technique shown in Figure5. Normally all resistors in the bridge configuration are chosen to be equal to each other. Therefore, the resulting output signal in this case will be zero voltage [20-21].

Figure5: Whetstone Bridge Configuration

However, in the case of the U-shaped cantilever, mechanical strain generated by bending leads to a change in the resistances of gauge positioned near the anchor of the suspended "U-shape," shown in Figure 1 [22].

The configuration of Wheatstone bridge which powered by voltage supply is considered as the standard technique to connect the piezoresistors. In this arrangement, the two gauges named as R1 and R4, are combined into the Wheatstone bridge together with the two reference resistors, R2 and R3, which are located on the bulk material [23]. For sensor applications, it is essential that at least one of the resistors must be sensitive to the measured parameter. This ensures that any variation in resistance caused by mechanical strain is accurately detected and converted into a corresponding electrical output signal.

In this study, at least one of the resistors in bridge configuration must depends on the parameter being measured. Then the variation in resistance is utilized to convert the mechanical response of the cantilever into the corresponding electrical signal. The differential output voltage (V_{out}) of the Wheatstone bridge is derived by using Equation6 [23-24].

$$V_{out} = V_{CC} \frac{R_2 R_3 - (R_1 + \Delta R_1)(R_4 + \Delta R_4)}{((R_1 + \Delta R_1) + R_3)(R_2 + (R_4 + \Delta R_4))} \quad (6)$$

Where:

- V_{out} denotes the differential output voltage

- V_{CC} represents the voltage source
- R_1, R_2, R_3 and R_4 are the Wheatstone bridge resistors
- ΔR_1 and ΔR_4 denote the change in the bridge resistances due to strain in the piezoresistors

When the Wheatstone bridge under balanced condition, i.e. at the equilibrium between the resistive element, the differential output voltage (V_{out}) becomes zero and the multiplication of the bridge resistances will be opposite diagonal as shown in Equation 7 [25].

$$R_1 \cdot R_4 = R_2 \cdot R_3 \quad (7)$$

On the other hand, when the Wheatstone bridge is not in the balance condition the differential output voltage (V_{out}) can be measured. As previously noticed, the piezoresistive gauges are utilized to measure the low magnetic flux similar to that generated by the magnetic field of the Earth. Typically, the electrical signals measured by the piezoresistive gauges are significantly small. Therefore, high gain amplifiers with low noise are usually used to amplify the output signal obtained from the wheatstone bridge. These amplifiers also suppress the distortion and interference that are accompanied with the required signal to ensure correct and reliable measurements [25-26].

- **Magnetic field sensor sensitivity**

The sensitivity (S) of the magnetic field sensors is defined as the ratio between the output voltage of the measurement circuit and the detected magnetic flux density. This relationship is represented in Equation 8 [27]:

$$s = \frac{V_{out}}{B_{ext}} \quad (8)$$

Where:

- V_{out} is the output voltage
- B_{ext} represents the external magnetic flux density.

In this system, there are two types of sensitivities named: static sensitivity and resonant sensitivity. The static sensitivity (S_{static}) is defined as the performance of the sensors in the cantilever static mode when the cantilever does not vibrate and respond to the slow changing or constant magnetic fields. Conversely, the resonant sensitivity ($S_{resonant}$), denotes the dynamic mode when the cantilever operates at its resonant frequency during vibration. At this frequency, the system has normally high responsive and this allow to enhanced the detection of magnetic fields resulting from the amplified mechanical responses. The difference between the static sensitivity and resonant sensitivity is significant, since each mode affords different levels of measurement precision which depends on the sensor operating conditions [28].

3. Results and Discussions

- **Cantilever deflection against Lorentz force**

In this study when the deflection in a U-shaped cantilever carrying direct current due to the presence of the external magnetic field (Lorentz Force), two scenarios can be considered:

- **Static Condition**

When a direct current flows through the U-shaped cantilever placed in an orthogonal static magnetic field, the Lorentz force acts upon it. The magnitude of this force can be calculated using Equation 1. As a result, deflections occur along the arms of the cantilever, as previously demonstrated in Figure 1. In this case, the electric current and static magnetic field are assumed to be 100 mA and 12 mT, respectively. The cantilever's dimensions are also assumed to be 760 μm for the base and 1000 μm for the arm length [27-28].

By substituting these values into Equation 1:

$$\vec{F} = \vec{I}L \times \vec{B} \quad (1)$$

The corresponding Lorentz force acting on the base of the cantilever will be:

$$\vec{F} = 100 \times 760 \times 12 \times 10^{-6} \text{ N} = 0.912 \mu\text{N}$$

This force represents the Lorentz force generated due to the interaction between the current and the magnetic field. It results from the interaction between the DC current and the perpendicular magnetic field.

Figure 6 demonstrates the resulting cantilever deflection. A maximum displacement of 9.1 μm is observed at the base when a 0.912 μN force is applied in the negative z-direction (downward). This displacement reflects the mechanical strain that the cantilever can tolerate. This emphasizes how the Lorentz force in a static setup causes a measurable deflection in the cantilever.

Figure 6: 3D Simulation of Cantilever under 0.9 μN Downward Force

Secondly, upon applying the alternating current (AC) in the dynamic mode, the cantilever experiences resonance when the alternating current frequency matches the natural frequency of the cantilever. The resonance generated amplifies the deflection which considerably increases the

sensitivity of the device to magnetic fields. Operating near the resonance allows the detection of smaller magnetic flux changes and consequently improves the precision of measurements [27-29].

The displacement of the cantilever is considerably large when a periodic force is applied at the natural frequency of 3.019 kHz in the vibration mode, compared to the constant force applied in the static case. The observed displacement is approximately 45 μm . Table 1 compares the maximum displacement and sensitivity of the cantilever in both dynamic and static modes, with the same Lorentz force applied to the arms and base. In this scenario, a current of 100 mA and an external static magnetic field of 12 mT were supposed.

Table 1: The Displacement and Sensitivity of the Cantilever in Static and Dynamic Modes

Mode	Displacement (μm)	Sensitivity ($\mu\text{m}/\mu\text{N}$)
Static	9.1	10.1
Dynamic	45.2	50.2

Table1 illustrates that the sensitivity and the displacement of the cantilever are considerably improved when operated in the resonance mode compared to static mode. As shown in the Table when the displacement in static mode is 9.1 μm , the corresponding displacement in the dynamic (resonance) mode has comparably high value of 45.2 μm which shows substantial improvement. This significant increase in displacement indicates the effectiveness of applying the cantilever at the resonant frequency in order to attain high sensitivity. Furthermore, the sensitivity in dynamic mode (50.2 $\mu\text{m}/\mu\text{N}$) is approximately five times greater than in static mode (10.1 $\mu\text{m}/\mu\text{N}$). This ensures that operating the cantilever in dynamic mode significantly enhances its performance, hence small forces can be detected with relatively high precision [27-29].

- **Calculations of Piezo resistor**

To examine the change in the resistance of the piezo resistor, the constant force applied to the cantilever is varied, and the corresponding deflections were measured. The percent change in resistance ($\Delta R_p\%$) from the original value of piezoresistor resistance (R_p) denotes the unstressed position of the piezoresistor is then calculated. The value of R_p obtained from the simulation results is 1709.83 Ω . Sample of the results of $\Delta R_p\%$ for different values of the cantilever deflections are presented in Table2.

Table 2: Sample Simulation Results Illustrating Resistance Variation with Cantilever Deflection

Displacement (μm)	% change in R
5	0.056
12.5	0.061
20	0.07
25	0.085
30	0.107
35	0.132
40	0.16
45	0.192
50	0.223

The graph of Figure7 showed that, there is a nonlinear increase in the change of piezoresistor resistance with respect to the cantilever displacement increase [30].

Figure7: A Sample of Simulation Results Showing the Change in Resistance as A Function of Cantilever Deflections

The values of the percentage change in the resistance ($\Delta R_p\%$) obtained from the simulation are used to mathematically deduce the corresponding values of change in the resistance (ΔR_p) in ohms (Ω). This change in resistance is then implemented to the circuit of Wheatstone bridge shown in Figure5 to obtain the voltage output measurements. The CoventorWare software provides the output as percentage values of the unstressed (original) resistance of the piezoresistor. Equation5 described in the previous section is used to calculate the change in resistance (ΔR_p) depending of the value of the percentage change in the resistance. As an example, at the cantilever deflection

of 5 μm in the negative z-direction, the obtained value of ΔR_p 0.056, and if the calculated value of the unstressed resistor is 1709.83 Ω , then the corresponding calculated value of ΔR_p will be 0.96 Ω [30].

If the parameters of the Wheatstone bridge shown in Figure 5 are selected as follows:

$$V_{CC} = 5V, (R_1 + \Delta R_1) = (R_4 + \Delta R_4) = 1709.83 \Omega, \text{ and } R_2 = R_3 = 1710.79 \Omega,$$

Then the corresponding simulation results provide an output voltage (V_{out}) of 1.405 mV.

When these values are substituted into Equation 6,

$$V_{out} = V_{CC} \frac{R_2 R_3 - (R_1 + \Delta R_1)(R_4 + \Delta R_4)}{((R_1 + \Delta R_1) + R_3)(R_2 + (R_4 + \Delta R_4))}$$

then, the calculated output voltage will be 1.4033 mV, which indicates good agreement with the output voltage obtained from simulation results (1.405 mV), this agreement highlights the consistency of the calculated values and confirms that the values of the resistor used and the mathematical expressions are effective in expecting the output voltage in different conditions. In Table 3, the calculated change in resistance (ΔR_p) values and their corresponding output voltages are presented for various levels of cantilever deflection [30].

Table3: The Relationship Between Cantilever Deflection, Calculated ΔR_p Values, and the Estimated Output Voltage

Displacement (μm)	Output Voltage (mV)	Change in Resistor (Ω)
5	1.6	0.95
8	1.7	1.02
12	1.8	1.1
20	1.93	1.2
22	2.05	1.25
25	2.2	1.55
30	2.8	1.82
32	3	1.9
35	3.22	2.4

Figure 8 shows the relationship between these parameters and give emphasis on how the resistance and the output voltage are influenced by the changes in the deflection of the cantilever.

Figure 8: Correlation between cantilever deflection, calculated ΔR_p values, and output voltage estimation

The output signal of 1.545 mV is generated by the Lorentz force which results from an external static magnetic field of 10 mT. When these values were substituted in Equation 8 [31],

$$s = \frac{V_{out}}{B_{ext}} \quad (8)$$

then the approximate calculated value of sensitivity will be 0.155 mV/mT. In this paper, the output voltage is obtained directly from the Wheatstone bridge circuit. Nevertheless, the level of the electrical signal obtained from the piezoresistive gauges is usually very low and will be affected by noise and other unwanted signals, therefore on chip amplifier circuits with relatively high gain as well as noise reduction circuitry will be of great importance in order to achieve reliable measurements and readings [31].

Table 5 shows the sensitivity values and the percent change in the resistance which were compared across three different piezoresistor thicknesses determined by the thickness of the cantilever beam. In addition, Figure 9 provides a clear illustration of these relations. The results show that the thickness variation in piezoresistor results to a considerable effect in the performance and the sensitivity of the system which indicates the importance of the structure and size of the sensor in improving its efficiency. Table 5 shows the sensitivity values and percent change in resistance

compared across three different piezoresistor thicknesses, determined by the thickness of the cantilever beam.

Table 5: Simulation Results for the Percentage Change in Resistance Values for Different Beam Thicknesses Against Cantilever Deflections.

Displacement (μm)	Cantilever Deflection of Different Thicknesses		
	0.6 μm Thickness	3 μm Thickness	6 μm Thickness
5	0.012	0.053	0.076
12.5	0.014	0.064	0.082
20	0.02	0.075	0.125
25	0.035	0.087	0.163
30	0.051	0.11	0.207
35	0.072	0.137	0.258
40	0.077	0.138	0.268
45	0.081	0.151	0.299
50	0.091	0.164	0.33
55	0.1	0.178	0.361

The results shown in Table5 presents the percentage change in resistance across various displacements (in micrometers) for a cantilever beam with three different piezoresistor thicknesses: 0.6 μm , 3 μm , and 6 μm . As displacement increases, the percentage change in resistance also increases through all thicknesses. This reflects the direct relationship between deflection and strain in the piezoresistive material. Particularly, the 6 μm thickness gives the largest resistance change, reaching 0.361% at a 55 μm displacement, which indicates greater sensitivity and is advantageous for applications that requires exact detection of small deflections. On the other hand, the 3 μm and 0.66 μm thicknesses exhibit reasonable and lower sensitivity, respectively, such that the 0.6 μm thickness results show the smallest percentage change, signifying it as more stable and less responsive to the minor displacement changes. This advancement underlines the significance of piezoresistor thickness in the performance of the sensor, where the sensitivity is enhanced by thinner materials whereas the thicker layers' favor stability and durability. This makes the thickness selection critical to enhance the function of the sensor depending on the requirements of specific application.

Additionally, Figure 9 provides a clear demonstration of the relationships shown in Table5. The results indicate that the variations in piezoresistor thickness have a substantial effect on the system performance and sensitivity, underlining the significance of the structure and size of the sensor in increasing its efficiency.

Figure 9. Simulation Results for Percentage Change of Resistance Values for Different Beam Thicknesses Plotted Against Cantilever Deflections

In Table6 presents a comparative analysis of the piezoresistor resistance, resonant frequency, maximum displacement, and the percentage change in resistance for a U-shaped cantilever with embedded piezoresistors of changing thicknesses under a uniform Lorentz force at 10 mT magnetic flux. The results show that as the piezoresistor and silicon (Si) thicknesses increase, the maximum displacement and the resistance significantly decrease, however the resonant frequency increases, showing that the stability enhances with thicker materials but reduce the sensitivity. For instance, for piezoresistor of 0.6 μm thickness and Si of 2 μm thickness, the resistance, the maximum displacement and the percentage change of resistance will be 5557 Ω , 117.6 μm and 2.50 respectively. However, when the thicknesses of the piezoresistor and Si increases to 3 μm and 5 μm respectively, resistance, the maximum displacement and percentage change in the resistance reduce to 1710 Ω , 12.74 μm and 0.062 respectively. This give emphasis to how the increase in thickness strengthens the structural harshness and decreases the sensitivity.

TABLE 6: Simulation Results Showing Changes in Various Parameters for Different Thicknesses of the Piezoresistor

Si Thickness (μm)	Piezoresistor Thickness (μm)	Resistance (Ω)	Resonant Frequency (kHz)	Maximum Displacement (μm)	ΔR_p %
2	0.6	5557	2.117	117.6	2.50
5	3	1710	4.55	12.74	0.062
9	6	571	8	2.5	0.019
12	8	420	10.1	1.9	0.014
15	10	381	12.2	1.5	0.010
18	12	350	14.3	1.2	0.008
21	15	321	16.5	1	0.006

As shown in Table7 the theoretical values of the output voltage and the sensitivity for different thicknesses of the piezoresistor were reduced with the increase of the piezoresistor thinness which

indicates its influence on the sensor performance. It is observed that for small thickness of the piezoresistor (0.6 μm) a considerably high values of output voltage (6.35 mV) and sensitivity (64 mV/mT) were obtained. These values were significantly reducing with the increase of the piezoresistor thickness. For example, when the thickness is 12 μm the corresponding values of the output voltage and sensitivity are 0.31 μV and 0.03 mV/mT respectively. This indicates that smaller piezoresistor thickness values enhance the sensitivity and the voltage output, especially in applications that need a high response to magnetic fields [31].

Table7: Theoretical Values of Output Voltage and Sensitivity for Different Piezoresistor Thicknesses

Piezoresistor Thickness (μm)	Output Voltage (mV)	Sensitivity (mV/mT)
0.6	6.35	64
1	5.318	53.36
1.5	4.027	40.06
2	2.736	26.76
3	0.155	0.16
6	0.000634	0.06
9	0.00045	0.04
12	0.00031	0.03
15	0.00021	0.02
18	0.00015	0.015

4. Conclusion

This paper presents an analytical model supported by simulations to describe the vibration mode of U-shaped cantilever devices that are actuated by the Lorentz force. The results depicted that when exciting the cantilever at or near its natural frequency through a periodic force, it experiences considerably large displacement when compared with the only applied static force. Due to its easiness and efficiency, a piezoresistor is selected to function as a sensing element in order to convert this mechanical response into an electrical signal (output voltage). It is observed that the graph for the displacement as a function of applied force reveals a highly linear relationship for both dynamic and static force conditions. The analysis of the results also indicates that the percentage change in resistance ($\Delta R\%$) of a polysilicon piezoresistor is directly proportional to the deflections of the cantilever. The highest value of $\Delta R\%$ is noticed at the maximum displacement of the cantilever when driven at the resonant frequency. Based on the simulation results of the Wheatstone bridge circuit, the sensitivity of the cantilever increases considerably with the increase of the cantilever thicknesses.

References

1. Haoran Wen and Dr. Chong Li, MEMS-Based Sensors: Technology and Applications, 2023.

2. Mohammed Gad-el-Hak, MEMS: Introduction and Fundamentals, CRC Press, 2005.
3. Reza Ghodssi and Pinyen Lin, MEMS Materials and Processes Handbook, Springer, 2011.
4. Marc J. Madou, Fundamentals of Microfabrication and Nanotechnology, Three-Volume Set, CRC Press, 2018.
5. P. I. Oden and T. E. Schlesinger, MEMS Cantilevers and Their Applications in Sensing" Journals of Sensors and Actuators A: Physical, Elsevier, 2014.
6. Sunipa Roy and Chandan Kumar Sarkar, MEMS and Nanotechnology for Gas Sensors, CRC Press, 2016.
7. S. Arlett, E. Myers, and M. Roukes, "Micromachined Cantilever-Based Sensors", Nature Nanotechnology Journal, Nature Publishing Group, 2011.
8. Roger T. Howe and Richard S. Muller, Piezoresistor Design and Applications, 2008.
9. Nadim Maluf and Kirt Williams, Introduction to Microelectromechanical (MEMS) Systems, Artech House, 2004.
10. X. Wang and Y. Fang, "Modeling and Simulation of Electrostatic Actuated U-shaped Cantilever Beams", Sensors and Actuators A: Physical, Elsevier, 2012
11. Chang Liu, "Foundations of MEMS", Pearson, 2012
12. Stephen D. Senturia "Microsystem Design", Springer, 2000.
13. A. Boisen and T. Thundat , "Electrostatic Actuation and Microcantilever Sensors", Journal of Micromechanics and Microengineering, IOP Publishing, 2009.
14. Mohammad d I. Younis, "Micro Electro Mechanical Systems (MEMS), Springer, 2011.
15. Thomas B. Jones, "Electromechanics and MEMS", Cambridge University Press, 2013.
16. John W. Gardner "Piezoresistor Design and Applications", Springer, 2015.
17. X. Xu, T. Ma, and W. Liang, " Design and Simulation of High Sensitivity Piezoresistive MEMS Cantilevers", Journal of Micromechanics and Micro engineering, IOP Publishing, 2021.
18. Osman Ulkir a, Ishak Ertugrul b, Nihat Akkus c, Salih Ozer d , Production of piezoelectric cantilever using MEMS-based layered manufacturing technology, Science Direct, Optik, , Volume 273, 170472, February 2023.
19. Am Zhang and Wei Li, "Micro and Nano Fabrication of Piezoresistive Sensors", CRC Press, 2012.
20. **Chen, Q., Chasiotis, I., & Kulkarni, A.** (*Simulation Techniques for MEMS Devices: A Case Study Using CoventorWare*. *Microelectronics Journal*, Elsevier, 2014.
21. **Leicht, M., et al.** *Micro and Nano Scale Mechanical Testing of MEMS Structures*. *Journal of Micromechanics and Microengineering*, 2016.
22. **Yoon, Y. K., & Lee, J.** *Introduction to MEMS Transducers and Their Applications*, in *Advances in MEMS*
23. **Senturia, S. D.**, *Microsystem Design*, Kluwer Academic Publishers, 2001.

24. **Fraden, J.**, *Handbook of Modern Sensors: Physics, Designs, and Applications*, Springer, 2010.
25. J. Chen, Z. Wu, and H. Liu, "Performance Analysis of MEMS Piezoresistive Sensors Based on Wheatstone Bridge Circuits", *IEEE Sensors Journal*, IEEE. 2019.
26. S. Lee, Y. Kim, and J. Lee, "Wheatstone Bridge Circuit Design for High-Performance MEMS Pressure Sensors", *Microsystem Technologies*, Springer, 2017.
27. **Li, X., Zhang, W., & Fang, D.** "Analysis and Optimization of Piezoresistive Cantilever Sensors for Magnetic Field Detection.", *Journal of Microelectromechanical Systems*, 16(5), 1178-1185, 2007.
28. **Sun, Y., & Rogers, J.** "MEMS Resonators for Magnetic Field Sensing." *Nature Materials*, 6(8), 612-624, 2007.
29. **Reddy, K. S., & Gupta, V. K.**, "Development and Analysis of MEMS-Based Cantilever Magnetometer." *Sensors and Actuators A: Physical*, 141(2), 225-231, 2008.
30. **Dahiya, R. S., Valle, M., Adami, A., & Lorenzelli, L.**, *Piezoelectric Piezoresistive Sensors*. Springer, 2013.
31. **Yang, Y. J., Chuang, Y. J., & Fang, W.** "Magnetic and Temperature Sensitivity of Lorentz Force MEMS." *Sensors and Actuators A: Physical*, 135(2), 386-39, 2007.